

Scenario 1: Technology and Training: Advancing the Quality of Higher Education

In this scenario, a projection for the year 2040 in the Brazilian educational context will be presented. In this vision, we consider the widespread adoption of technology, accompanied by solid teacher training and improved quality of higher education. In this rapidly transforming global scenario, digitization in higher education is not only inevitable but already underway, accelerated by the pandemic. This process brings unique challenges and opportunities for the Brazilian educational system.

Technological advancements will have a greater impact on education due to the increased use of technological solutions in teaching. One of the main changes resulting from this will be the alteration of the professor's image as the sole source of knowledge, as access to information by the student will be easy and practical. Thus, learning will be more autonomous for the learner, and it will be necessary to change evaluation methods to assess whether the student possesses knowledge of the topic. Additionally, teachers will take on the role of motivators and learning experience consultants, and the use of flipped classrooms will be expanded.

Another aspect is the progression in the field of Artificial Intelligence, which will allow for personalized education to generate more suitable learning for each student. This personalization could occur in numerous ways, especially in the distance learning modality. Personalized education and autonomous learning, empowered by Artificial Intelligence, are central aspects of the future of higher education. Technology is a tool, not an end in itself, and it should be integrated to enrich the educational experience. For example, the system could recommend specific materials for students to fill gaps in the topics covered in the subject or because they are of greater interest to the student. The students' performance in evaluative activities or information from completed forms would identify these gaps and interests. As a result, there will be an increase in specialization in the profiles of graduated professionals and a decrease in dropout rates in higher education courses.

In education, mobile technologies, especially the development of 5G, will significantly impact teaching and make it more digital and distributed, enabling field research more easily and contributing to access to distance learning courses.

Other new technologies will be used in the classroom, such as 3D printing and robotics, assisting and enhancing the teaching process. However, there will be a risk of increasing social exclusion and inequality due to inequality in access to technologies, which could be mitigated with appropriate public policies. Effective public policies are essential to ensure that technological innovations benefit all students, addressing socioeconomic disparities. Furthermore, technological advancement will require individuals to take updating or adaptation courses in higher education institutions to remain relevant in the job market.

Regarding economic aspects, education will be subject to the interests of economic groups that are oriented towards profit, especially in private institutions. However, to remain competitively relevant in the market and keep up with trends, these institutions would need to invest in technological solutions and improve the quality of education. Thus, concerns about economic issues would not harm education.

Some social aspects will also be relevant. For example, due to the increasing inequality between social classes in higher education, individuals from lower income brackets will have more difficulty accessing colleges, requiring affirmative policies to address the issue. Additionally, there will be an increase in gender equity policies in all higher education courses where there is underrepresentation, reducing the gender distribution inequality among courses. Maintaining a balance between technological advancements and the preservation of the quality of humanistic education is vital, ensuring that technology serves as an enhancement tool rather than a replacement for educational essence.

The risks of the “McDonaldization” of higher education – due to the participation of economic groups interested in expanding and exploiting the private educational market – will be offset by the benefits in advancement, distribution, and technological adoption. Thus, there will be a potential increase in the quality of higher education in the coming years, including distance education courses.

In parallel with this process, in the face of a more dynamic job market, there will be a popularization of short-term courses (e.g., polytechnic courses) competing with more traditional forms of higher education. From this perspective, the quality of graduated professionals will also remain relatively stable or higher than current levels. Additionally, higher education courses that do not have regulations to practice the profession will not have a large demand for students, as the number of technical courses will increase to meet the demand for professionals.

Another trend focusing on reducing dropout rates is greater flexibility of universities to their courses according to students' preferences, thus favoring the training of students with a more academic profile or who are more interested in entering the job market. Part of this movement will be related to the growth of career guidance activities from high school onwards and will continue during graduation.

These changes will require ongoing training of teachers to be constantly updated on new teaching methodologies, techniques, and tools used. Collaboration between educational institutions and industry is essential to provide a more practical education aligned with the job market's needs. Equally important is the continuous development of teachers, especially in educational technologies, to adapt to the new demands of teaching. At this point, the ability to reinvent oneself over time and adapt to high technological dynamism will be fundamental attributes for a new generation of teachers.

There will also be a new opportunity for transformation in universities' physical spaces and infrastructure. Firstly, due to the nature of distance education courses as a highly scalable teaching modality as a business model, which dispenses with the physical classroom as a fundamental element for pedagogical practice. Secondly, there is a need to redesign classrooms to support hybrid and asynchronous teaching, in addition to the inclusion of new technological devices that will allow the exploration of virtual and augmented realities as didactic tools. Thus, the designs of architectural spaces in educational buildings will emphasize the possibility for students, mediated by technology, to explore a hybrid and digital experience of encounter, coexistence, and exchange of ideas.

In addition to the transformations related to technological and socioeconomic aspects directly involved in the context of higher education, some exogenous and global factors related to mental health and environmental crises may directly influence the transformation of higher education in Brazil.

Considering that depression and other mental disorders will be one of the main factors causing students to drop out of higher education courses, digital tools that support the teaching-learning process (such as eLearning platforms), as they become more powerful in learning about their users, may present features designed to reduce dropout due to demotivation. We must pay special attention to student's mental health and well-being, balancing technological innovation with a learning environment that promotes the students' holistic development.

Due to climate change, there will be an increase in demand for professionals and higher education courses related to ESG issues, where, naturally, course curricula will be redesigned to align with the international sustainable development agenda.